

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D8.3 Liability Landscape

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Executive Summary

Liability in Artificial Intelligence in healthcare, especially in AI-assisted surgery, is an emerging issue with significant implications for patients, surgeons, clinical adoption, and regulatory oversight. We conducted normative legal, interdisciplinary, and empirical research (focus groups with surgeons from the EU and the US) to understand better the legal frameworks that may govern liability for patient injuries related particularly to the use of AI-driven technologies in surgery, the risks and regulation of AI development more generally, and to assess surgeons' views concerning liability for using AI-driven technology in surgery. During our research, we examined and answered questions, such as: Who may be held liable under current law in the EU and US if an AI-assisted surgery goes wrong? Should surgeons be concerned about possible liability when using such tools? What could a balanced liability system look like to facilitate the uptake of AI? We also co-organised the *Life Sciences AI Summit – Europe*, an impactful stakeholder conference on regulatory, legal, and compliance frameworks for AI in Brussels.

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List of Acronyms, Definitions, and Abbreviations

ACE	Automated capsule endoscopy
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
CADe	Computer-aided detection
CADx	Computer-aided diagnosis
CBE	Changes Being Effected
Current PLD	Current Product Liability Directive
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FDA	US Food and Drug Administration
FDCA	US Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act
GenAI	Generative AI
HIPAA	US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
LLM	Large Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
New PLD	New Product Liability Directive
PHI	Protected health information
Proposed AILD	Proposed AI Liability Directive
Proposed PLD	Proposed Product Liability Directive
Surgical video data	Surgical video and the associated metadata
UC	University of Chicago and its medical center
US	United States

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being used in healthcare and health research contexts but raises numerous legal liability challenges [1]–[8]. Outstanding liability questions include, but are not limited to, whether uncertainty about liability presents barriers to the use of potentially beneficial medical AI systems by healthcare providers and the standard of care applicable to healthcare providers who use these AI-driven technologies. Before adopting technologies, it is important to understand who will be responsible when they cause injuries. Without this knowledge, developers, physicians, hospitals, and patients may make suboptimal decisions about whether to develop, adopt, and use AI-driven technologies. For example, they may adopt very risky products because they do not think there is any liability risk, or they may not adopt them at all to avoid what they view as a high risk. Task 8.3 ‘Liability’, led by UIUC, has sought to explore these and other liability questions raised by AI-driven technologies in surgery by:

- (1) conducting normative legal analysis of the legal frameworks that may govern liability for injuries related specifically to the use of AI-driven technology in clinical care;
- (2) conducting an empirical study assessing surgeons’ views relating to liability for using AI-driven technology in surgery.

First, we have sought to examine the existing and developing legal framework that may govern liability for damage caused by the use of AI-driven technology in clinical care. Currently, there is no fully harmonised legal framework for liability caused by the use of AI-driven technology in surgery in place in either the European Union (EU) or the United States (US). Additionally, there are currently no medical liability cases that address injuries caused by medical AI systems [9]. However, the European Commission (EC) has taken several steps to address the issue of liability, such as publishing a *Report on the Safety and Liability Implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and Robotics* (2020) [10] and two proposed Directives in 2022 dealing with liability for AI systems: a proposed Product Liability Directive (Proposed PLD) [11] and a proposed AI Liability Directive (Proposed AILD) [12]. In particular, the revised PLD (New PLD) was published in the EU’s Official Journal in November 2024 and entered into force recently on 8 December 2024 [13]. The Member States must transpose the New PLD into national law by 9 December 2026 (Art. 22(1)), after which the New PLD will apply to products marketed from that date [13]–[14]. In other words, the current 1985 PLD (Current PLD) remains applicable to those products placed on the market before 9 December 2026 [15]. However, the EC withdrew its Proposed AILD in February 2025, and it is currently unclear whether it will introduce another similar or different proposal in the future [16]. We have examined the current and proposed liability frameworks to identify and answer questions about legal liability for using medical AI systems, like the CLASSICA cancer classification system currently in development, in patient care.

Second, we have sought to understand the broader socio-legal issues that impact AI development and regulations across all sectors by engaging in normative research with interdisciplinary colleagues to identify and comment on the ongoing efforts to govern AI generally through horizontal regulation. This included research into issues of data privacy as well as an examination of the benefits and risks of AI generally that influence patient safety and legal liability concerns as new AI technologies are increasingly introduced into the health sector.

Finally, we have sought to identify challenges and opportunities gleaned from surgeons’ perspectives on the standard of care for surgeons who use these technologies in the US and EU. By communicating

directly with surgeons regarding their current knowledge, opinions, understanding, and experience with both AI-driven technologies and medical liability, we were able to identify the relevant liability issues that should be investigated and addressed to facilitate the development of a fair liability framework to govern the development and use of AI-driven technologies in surgery [17].

2 Approach

The main goal of Task 8.3 was to analyse the current legal landscape and new developments in the EU and US related to liability for the use of AI-assisted or autonomous medical tools. To accomplish this goal, we carried out normative and empirical legal analysis, research, and writing to answer the questions below:

- Who may be held liable under current law if an AI-supported operation goes wrong: the surgeon, the hospital, or the AI manufacturer?
- What are surgeons' perspectives on liability for using AI-supported surgical tools?
- What steps can individual and organisational healthcare providers take to avoid potential litigation in AI-supported operations?
- What would a balanced liability system look like to facilitate the uptake of AI?
- What legal issues relating to AI development and design generally impact horizontal regulation of AI across all industries?

To answer these questions, we conducted normative and empirical legal research. We also approached research questions through comparative and interdisciplinary lenses, considering medical AI systems, like the CLASSICA cancer classification system currently in development.

2.1 Normative Research Approach and Methodology

2.1.1 *Legal Doctrinal Research*

Our normative legal doctrinal research involved the review and analysis of regulatory and liability law and the associated literature in the EU and the US to map the liability framework in each jurisdiction. We explored liability implications of primary sources of law, including: (1) newly proposed (and recently adopted) EU law governing liability for AI-caused injury and regulation of AI generally and (2) US law governing medical and product liability, recent relevant US case law, and the privacy and sharing of health information.

2.1.2 *Contextual Research*

Our normative contextual research involved the review and analysis of medical and legal literature, including news articles, academic and industry journal articles, and government reports and websites to monitor technological, medical, and legislative developments concerning AI technology. Our contextual research, which is focused on identifying and evaluating liability issues for AI-driven technology in the larger socio-political context, covered both legal aspects of AI generally and the use of AI-driven technologies for healthcare. This work allowed us to understand trends in AI technology uptake and adoption in the medical sector, their impact on medical liability in the EU and US, and the development of horizontal and vertical legal frameworks that might govern AI-driven technologies in surgery.

2.1.3 Interdisciplinary Research

Our interdisciplinary normative research involved collaboration with medical, surgical, and technical experts to examine literature in these corresponding expert domains for impacts on liability using medical AI, including AI-driven technologies in surgery. Through collaborations in interdisciplinary teams, we reviewed and analysed use cases for AI-driven applications in medicine, medical and computer science research results and literature, and primary and secondary legal sources to examine potential legal implications of AI development and deployment generally, in medicine, and in surgery.

2.2 Empirical Research Approach and Methodology

We conducted empirical research to better understand surgeons' perspectives on liability for the use of AI-driven technologies in surgery. We designed and carried out a focus group study with surgeon participants in the EU and US to explore their perspectives on liability for using AI technology in their surgical practice [17]. We developed a focus group guide based on the medical and legal literature that also contained hypothetical cases about AI-driven technology in colorectal surgery [17]. We recruited participants through a call for participation that we shared in personal and professional networks [17]. We aimed for diverse participation across race, ethnicity, age, gender, geography, and experience, when possible [17].

The inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) adults (minimum 18 years old); (2) surgeons based in an EU Member States or in the US, preferably those specialising in gastrointestinal surgery to enhance discussions related to our hypothetical cases about a colorectal surgical procedure; (3) the ability to read and communicate comfortably in English; (4) the willingness to consent to participation; and (5) a commitment to maintaining the confidentiality of the focus group meeting content, participants, and discussions [17]. We held six focus groups on Zoom that included 18 participants, comprised of 11 surgeons from the EU and seven from the US [17]. Focus groups were recruited and conducted from February to June 2023 by two team members (PI Sara Gerke and Mindy Duffourc) [17]. Both video and audio from each focus group meeting were recorded, and one team member (Duffourc) also took notes during these meetings [17]. Gerke and Duffourc independently validated the Zoom transcripts by viewing and listening to the recordings, as well as rereading the transcripts [17]. They then took reasonable means to de-identify/anonymise the validated transcripts and notes [17]. The anonymised study data were then shared with the UCPH team [17]. One of the UCPH team members (Mathia Møllebæk) qualitatively analysed the anonymised transcripts [17]. An inductive content analysis approach was employed to identify emergent content themes over two coding cycles [17]. After every coding cycle, initial reports on the results were distributed to the entire research team for review, ensuring their reliability and confirmability [17]. The team then validated the final results for publication [17]. The Institutional Review Board at the Pennsylvania State University (PSU) determined that this study met the criteria for exempt research (STUDY00021889) on January 20, 2023 [17]. We also received ethical approval from the UCPH's Institutional Review Board (504-0112/23-4000) for this study on January 30, 2023 [17]. We also treated any information identifying participants as "Confidential Information" in accordance with a confidentiality agreement that the PSU research team participants signed [17]. The UCPH team had access only to anonymous information [17]. The focus group study is discussed in depth in Section 3.2.

3 Results

3.1 Normative Legal Research on AI Liability and Governance

There are no liability rules that specifically govern liability for AI-driven technology in surgery or even liability for medical AI technologies more broadly. Thus, to understand how liability for AI-driven technologies in surgery might be governed, we conducted the following normative legal research. First, we mapped the liability framework for medical injuries in the US and EU and examined this framework in the context of medical AI, including AI-assisted surgery (Section 3.1.1). Second, we examined liability for AI-caused medical injuries and liability for using health data to develop medical AI to understand the full scope of AI's impact on liability in the healthcare context (Section 3.1.2).

3.1.1 Mapping the Liability Framework in the EU and the US

We conducted an in-depth examination of the legal liability frameworks that will govern liability for AI-driven medical technology in both the EU and the US. This comparative research identified challenges that AI-driven medical technologies present to both jurisdictions' legal frameworks. We also identified new developments in EU and US law that attempt to address these challenges and the benefits and drawbacks of these new legal developments. The results of our research were reported in the following publications: (1) The Proposed EU Directives for AI Liability Leave Worrying Gaps Likely to Impact Medical AI in *npj Digital Medicine* [18], (2) Decoding US Tort Liability in Healthcare's Black-Box AI Era: Lessons From the EU in *Stanford Technology Law Review* [19], (3) Liability for Use of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine in *Research Handbook on Health, AI and the Law* [9], (4) Medical AI and Tort Liability in *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* [20], (5) New Caselaw and Liability Risks for Manufacturers of Medical AI in *Science* [21], (6) A Comprehensive Labeling Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML)-Based Medical Devices in *Emory Law Journal* [22], and (7) *Chevron's Fall and Its Impact on Medical AI in Health Affairs Forefront* [23].

3.1.1.1 Identifying Existing Frameworks in the EU and the US

The liability frameworks for health injuries caused by AI-driven technologies in both the EU and the US focus on two main types of tort liability: (1) liability for manufacturers and (2) liability for individual and organisational healthcare providers [9], [19].

3.1.1.1.1 Manufacturer Liability

In both jurisdictions, manufacturers can be either strictly liable for injuries caused by defective products or liable under fault-based rules for injuries caused by the manufacturer's negligence [19, pp. 18-27, 33-35].

3.1.1.1.1.1 EU

In the EU, strict manufacturer liability is governed by the Current PLD (Arts. 19, 20, 22) as incorporated into Member States' national law [15], [19, p. 33]. Negligent manufacturer liability is governed by Member States' national fault-based law [19, p. 34]. Additionally, the EC proposed two Directives in 2022, one being the Proposed PLD, which is intended to amend strict product liability rules [11]. Only recently, on 8 December 2024, the New PLD (Art. 23) entered into force [14]. The New PLD (Art. 22(1)) must be transposed into Member States' national law by 9 December 2026 [14]. The New PLD will then

apply to products put on the market from that date [14]. However, the Current PLD will remain applicable for those products marketed before 9 December 2026 [14].

The Current PLD, which is already transposed into each Member States' national law, governs strict product liability of AI-driven products [19, p. 33]. Under the Current PLD (Art. 1), manufacturers are strictly liable for injuries caused by defective products [19, p. 33]. Notably, products under the Current PLD (Art. 2) encompass only movables, and thus, AI models, as intangibles, would likely only be considered a product if the AI is embedded into a movable, tangible product [19, p. 33].

AI-driven products would be considered defective under the Current PLD (Art. 6(1)) if they violate consumers' expectations of safety, which is determined by considering the product's presentation, its reasonably foreseeable use, and the moment of its entry on the market [19, p. 33]. For AI-driven products used in the healthcare sector, it is important to note that the Court of Justice of the European Union noted that consumers who are patients have "particularly high" expectations of safety [19, p. 33], [24]. Additionally, risk-utility factors, like whether there was a reasonable alternative design, can impact whether or not an AI-driven product is considered defective under the Current PLD (Art. 2) [19, p. 33].

Manufacturers of AI-driven products might avoid liability under the Current PLD (Art. 7) if: (1) the defect did not exist when the product entered the market; (2) the product was not sold or distributed for an "economic purpose;" (3) the product's defect was caused by the manufacturer's compliance with mandatory regulations; or (4) "the state of scientific and technical knowledge at the time when [the manufacturer] put the product into circulation was not such as to enable the existence of the defect to be discovered" ("development risk" or "state-of-the-art" defence) [19, pp. 33–34].

In addition to strict product liability under the Current PLD, Member States' national fault-based liability laws might impose liability for manufacturers' negligence [19, p. 34]. Under the general tort principles underlying Member States' fault-based liability law, manufacturers can be liable for injuries caused by their faulty conduct (i.e., a failure to act reasonably under the circumstances) relating to the design and manufacturing of the product, the warnings and information provided with the product, or product monitoring [19, pp. 34–35].

3.1.1.1.1.2 US

In the US, both strict and negligent manufacturer liability are governed primarily by state tort law [19, p. 18]. Generally, manufacturers can be strictly liable for injuries caused by defective products; however, we note that it is currently unclear whether courts would consider AI to be a product for the sake of product liability law [9, p. 161], [19, pp. 18–19]. On the one hand, software is considered a "good" in commercial law; on the other hand, software might not be considered "tangible personal property" amenable to governance by product liability law [19, p. 19], [see 25]. Courts might also likely draw a distinction between whether the software is considered a medical device under the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act [22, "it is likely that product liability law applies to AI/ML-based *medical devices*"].

Assuming AI is considered a product, an AI-driven product would be defective if it is determined to be unreasonably dangerous [19, p. 19]. Unlike strict liability, which focuses on the condition of the product, negligent product liability focuses on the behaviour of the manufacturer that led to the defective condition of the product [19, p. 19]. In practice, the legal analysis of strict product liability and negligent product liability seeks to determine whether a product was defective [19, p. 19]. There

are three main types of product defects: (1) design defects; (2) manufacturing defects; and (3) marketing defects related to the product’s instructions and warnings [19, p. 20].

Whether an AI-driven product’s design is defective is determined under either the “consumer expectations” test, the “risk-utility” test, or a combination of the two [19, pp. 20–22]. The consumer expectations test considers whether the product is reasonably safe for the product’s intended or reasonably foreseeable use [19, p. 20]. The risk-utility test considers whether the product’s risks outweigh its benefits by considering such factors as (1) whether a reasonable alternative design existed at the time the product entered the market; (2) the probability that the product would cause harm; (3) the product’s usefulness; and (4) the cost of eliminating risks of harm both financially and in terms of impact on the product’s utility [19, pp. 21–22].

Manufacturing defects occur when the product is not manufactured in accordance with its intended design, such as poor materials or workmanship [19, p. 22]. In contrast, marketing defects occur when manufacturers fail to provide sufficient notice, either pre- or post-market, about the reasonably foreseeable risks of using their product [19, pp. 23–24].

Manufacturers might avoid product liability in the US, particularly in the case of AI, if: (1) the AI is considered an AI-based medical device and receives marketing approval [19, p. 24], [26], [see 9, pp. 161–165], [see 20, pp. 98–100]; (2) the AI’s design is “unavoidably unsafe” [19, p. 25], [see 27]; (3) the AI “conformed to the state of the art in existence at the time the product was . . . manufactured” [19, p. 25], [28]; (4) if the AI is a medical device used by a physician and the manufacturer properly warned the physician of the risks (“learned intermediary doctrine”) [19, p. 25], [see 29], [22]; and/or (5) if the product was misused, altered, or modified in an unforeseeable manner or if the claimant was negligent or knowingly assumed risks [19, p. 27].

3.1.1.1.2 Healthcare Provider Liability in the EU and US

In both the EU and the US, liability for healthcare providers is generally determined under fault-based rules in tort law [19, pp. 27–30, 35–37]. Fault-based liability is governed primarily at the Member State level in the EU and at the state level in the US. Although we cannot individually discuss the fault-based liability law in each Member State and each US state, we note that the general legal principles underlying fault-based liability for healthcare providers in all relevant jurisdictions are similar [19, p. 63]. Healthcare providers can include individual providers, like surgeons, physicians, and nurses, or organisational healthcare providers, like hospitals or clinics. In the case of AI-driven technology, this means that healthcare providers are liable when their fault (or negligence) causes an injury [19, pp. 27, 35].

In general, individual healthcare providers are at fault when they breach a professional standard of care. US courts articulate this standard as the “degree of reasonable care and skill expected of members of the medical profession under the same or similar circumstances” [19, p. 28], [30]. In the EU, Member States generally refer to an objective standard of care corresponding to the healthcare provider’s field or *lex artis* [19, p. 35], [see 31]. In both jurisdictions, experts are generally required to establish the relevant standards of care [19, pp. 29, 35]. Individual healthcare providers who use AI-driven tools in their practice are required to comply with the standard of care governing their speciality, which considers the current state of medicine and the existing medical and surgical practice guidelines [19, pp. 29, 35]. For example, if the relevant practice guidelines prohibited physicians from using AI-driven technology on a certain patient population, and the doctor violated these guidelines

and caused the patient injury, the doctor might be liable if an expert determined that the doctor’s violation of the guidelines in that specific case breached the standard of care.

Organisational healthcare providers can incur two different types of liability related to the use of AI-driven technology in the organisation. First, they can be vicariously liable for the fault (or negligence) of individual healthcare providers in their employment [19, pp. 27–28, 35]. For example, if a hospital doctor breached the standard of care in treating a patient with AI-driven technology, the hospital might also be liable for the patient’s injury. Second, organisational healthcare providers can also be directly liable for their own fault [19, pp. 27, 29, 35]. Organisational providers might be at fault if they were negligent in hiring or training healthcare providers who work in the organisation [19, pp. 29, 35]. For example, if a hospital failed to train a nurse on the proper use of AI-driven technology in patient care and this led to a patient injury, the hospital might be directly liable to the patient. Healthcare organisations might also be at fault if they failed to properly maintain their equipment and facilities [19, pp. 29, 35]. For example, if a hospital failed to monitor and update AI-driven technology and this failure caused a patient injury, the hospital could be directly liable to the patient.

3.1.1.1.3 Evaluation of Recent Developments in the US Liability Framework

3.1.1.1.3.1 Manufacturer Liability and Preemption

In the US, a manufacturer sued by an injured patient under state law can assert several different defences. One crucially important defence argues that federal law expressly prohibits imposing state law liability on device manufacturers that have complied with federal law. Known as “express preemption,” this defence is available when state laws impose “any requirement . . . which is different from, or in addition to, any [federal] requirement applicable under this Act [US Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act; FDCA] to the device, and . . . which relates to the safety or effectiveness of the device” (FDCA § 521(a); 21 U.S.C. § 360k(a)).

While this provision overrides some state law claims, it does not override them all. For express preemption to kick in, the state law must conflict with a federal requirement. Under Supreme Court precedent, what counts as a federal requirement depends on how intensively the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) reviews the device [see 32]–[33], [21]. Because the FDA reviews devices according to risk, high-risk devices (Class III) usually involve the most intense review for safety and effectiveness, typically requiring clinical trial data—Premarket Approval (PMA) [21]. Express preemption blocks many state law claims against devices that received a PMA [see 33], [21], [9, p. 164], [20, p. 99]. By contrast, moderate-to-low-risk devices (Class II and Class I) usually involve less intensive review (if at all) and are more vulnerable to claims under state law [21]. One type of review, called Premarket Notification or 510(k), typically does not require clinical trial data [21]. Instead, the manufacturer must demonstrate its device is “substantially equivalent” to a legally marketed device (called “predicate”) (FDCA § 513(i)(1); 21 U.S.C. § 360c(i)(1)) [21]. Express preemption does not apply to 510(k)-cleared devices because the review is not sufficient to constitute a “requirement” [see 32], [21], [9, p. 164], [20, pp. 98–99].

That leaves one other type of review, the De Novo Classification Request or the De Novo process—for novel moderate-to-low-risk devices without a predicate—which requires more intensive review than 510(k) clearance and less intensive review than a PMA (e.g., some smaller amount of clinical data) [21]. Here, an open question remains about whether express preemption applies. There are only a few

decisions on this topic. One, a recent federal district court case in Louisiana, *Dickson v. Dexcom Inc.*, 2024, 2:24-CV-00121, addressed this question head-on.

The court issued two opinions [34]–[35]. In the first one, the court held the plaintiff’s breach of express warranty and design defect claims expressly pre-empted [34], [21]. The court found that express preemption applied because the FDA had codified regulations (special controls) about risk and mitigation measures concerning the device type at issue (i.e., a De Novo-authorized Class II “[i]ntegrated continuous glucose monitoring system”) (21 C.F.R. § 862.1355) [34], [21]. In other words, the court held that the codified regulations constituted federal requirements, and because the state law claims would have imposed requirements “in addition to” those federal requirements, the court held the claims expressly preempted [34], [21]. However, the court allowed the plaintiff to amend her failure to warn claim by giving the plaintiff a chance to show additional evidence that the manufacturer should have updated the label based on “newly acquired information on the risk of harm” under the “Changes Being Effected” (CBE) regulations (see 21 C.F.R. §§ 814.39(d)(2), 314.70(c)(6)(iii)) [34], [21]. In its second opinion, the court clarified that the CBE regulation only applies to PMA devices [35], [21]. It then assumed that even if a similar mechanism existed for De Novo devices, the plaintiff did not provide sufficient evidence to substantiate her claim [35], [21]. Consequently, the court also dismissed the plaintiff’s failure to warn claim, holding that it is expressly pre-empted [35], [21].

The decision is important because its answer to the novel legal question about liability protection could influence the behaviour of manufacturers of medical devices, including those based on AI/ML. Express preemption offers significant legal protection. If the De Novo process provides the same liability protection as the PMA process but requires less evidence, manufacturers may pursue devices that fit within the De Novo process [21]. However, the *Dickson* case alone will not provide a strong incentive for manufacturers to use the De Novo pathway because the US court system operates hierarchically [21]. In other words, a district court decision does not set precedent for all fifty states, or even a particular region within a federal circuit. More certainty is likely to come from decisions by the federal courts of appeals or the US Supreme Court, though it is unclear when [21]. Greater certainty could also come from Congress, which could also pass a law to clarify the effect of the express preemption provision on De Novo-authorized devices, perhaps by creating a system in which the default is *no* preemption, but manufacturers could apply for it through a process regulated by the FDA [21]. The FDA could also increase certainty without Congressional intervention by promulgating regulations mimicking those for PMA devices, which allow lawsuits based on manufacturers’ failure to update labels with newly acquired risk information [21].

3.1.1.1.3.2 Regulatory Changes Affecting Liability

The US regulatory and liability systems are tightly intertwined. How the FDA reviews a device can influence whether and when the manufacturer can be liable for injuries it causes. This means that whether and what kind of power the FDA has to review a device is important. Under the FDCA, Congress has granted the FDA broad authority to regulate devices [23]. To implement the Congressional grant of authority, the FDA promulgates regulations, which set binding legislative rules that regulated entities must follow. For the rules to meet the procedural requirements and have legal effect, the FDA typically must use informal (notice and comment) rulemaking.

Inevitably, implementing statutes through rulemaking involves interpreting the instructions Congress provided in the statute. Since the 1984 decision of *Chevron U.S.A., Inc. v. NRDC*, 467 U.S. 837, courts have deferred to reasonable agency interpretations when statutory language was ambiguous [23].

However, in the 2024 case of *Loper Bright Enterprises v. Raimondo*, the Supreme Court overruled *Chevron* and held that the courts do *not* need to defer to reasonable interpretations of ambiguous statutes by an agency [23]. Instead, a court reviewing an agency’s interpretation of a statute must determine “best” interpretation of the statute [23]. While it may consider the agency’s views about the statute’s meaning, it is not hidebound by them [23].

This is important in the AI/ML context because the FDA has primarily signalled its policies and positions through the publication of a series of nonbinding policy and guidance documents rather than through issuing regulations [23]. However, courts do not need to defer to nonbinding guidance documents [23]. And after *Loper Bright* courts are likely to treat them with even greater suspicion [23]. Additionally, the FDA’s approach may, ironically, become the subject of judicial review precisely because it has relied on nonbinding, rather than binding, rules [23]. Indeed, there is some precedent to suggest that courts may treat guidance documents as binding legislative rules when agencies use them to circumvent the statutorily required rulemaking process [23], [see 36].

The implications for liability are quite significant. For example, currently, federal law excludes certain software functions from the definition of medical devices, effectively placing them beyond the purview of the FDA (FDCA §§ 201(h)(1), 520(o); 21 U.S.C. § 321(h)(1), 360j(o)) [23]. Software that falls within this exclusion is subject to the full panoply of state law liability claims. But if it does not, then complicated regulatory schemes apply that may decrease state law liability (under preemption). Crucially, *Loper Bright* impacts the FDA’s authority to define what software falls within or outside the medical device definition by changing how much deference courts afford to the FDA’s interpretations of statutes [23]. As a result, courts will play an even greater role in defining the scope of the FDA’s authority and the scope of tort liability [23].

3.1.1.1.4 Evaluation of Recent Developments in the EU Liability Framework

In 2022, the EC proposed two new Directives: a proposed Product Liability Directive (Proposed PLD) [11] and a proposed AI Liability Directive (Proposed AILD) to address the challenges that AI technologies present for liability law [12, Explanatory Memorandum]. These two proposed Directives seek to ensure legally responsible AI through ex-post liability rules. They have an overarching goal to govern digital risks, including AI technologies, in a manner that balances the interests of beneficial innovation with the rights of injured parties [12, Explanatory Memorandum], [11, Explanatory Memorandum]. Both Directives were proposed shortly after the EU proposed the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act, which seeks to protect fundamental rights and ensure safety in connection with AI technologies through ex-ante regulation [37]. This approach stems from the EC’s view that “[s]afety and liability are two sides of the same coin: they apply at different moments and reinforce each other” [12, Explanatory Memorandum].

Both the New PLD (Art. 23) [13] and AI Act (Art. 113) [38] came into force on 8 December 2024 [14] and 1 August 2024 [39], respectively. The New PLD (Art. 22(1)) must be transposed into national law as a Directive by 9 December 2026 [13]–[14], while the AI Act is directly applicable in all EU Member States as a Regulation. The AI Act (Art. 113) will fully apply from 2 August 2026 with a few exceptions

[38]. However, the EC withdrew its Proposed AILD in February 2025, and it remains uncertain whether the EC will present an alternative proposal, whether similar or different, in the future [16].

For Task 8.3, we examined the Proposed PLD and Proposed AILD and their applicability to AI-driven medical technologies and determined that while they address some challenges related to AI-specific risks and information asymmetry, they still fail to adequately address liability for black-box medical AI [18].

Manufacturers are still strictly liable for defective products under the Proposed PLD [18]. However, several new provisions in the Proposed PLD make progress toward addressing liability challenges in cases of AI-caused injuries [18]. First, the Proposed PLD includes software in its definition of “product” in Article 4(1) [11] [18]–[19, p. 39]. It also recognises (Art. 6(1)(e)) the ability of black-box AI to change after market entry by expanding the scope of liability to include products still under the control of the manufacturer rather than focusing on market entry only [11], [18]–[19, p. 66]. Under Article 4(5), “manufacturer’s control” includes software upgrades or updates, or modifications. Additionally, Article 6(1)(c) integrates the continuous self-learning characteristic of some deep learning AI technologies as a characteristic that affects whether the product is “defective” [11], [18]–[19, pp. 66–67]. Fourth, the Proposed PLD (Art. 8) provides procedural rules that can help claimants who suffer an injury caused by AI to obtain evidence from defendants [11], [18]. Finally, Article 9(4) allows the court to presume that the AI is defective and/or that a defective AI caused the claimant’s injuries in cases where “technical or scientific complexity” makes it “excessive[ly] difficult[.]” to prove these elements of product liability [11], [18]–[19, p. 39].

Unfortunately, the Proposed PLD’s criteria for determining whether or not a product is defective still does not address the challenges posed by some black-box AI models [18]. Under Article 6(1), a product is considered defective if it “does not provide the safety which the public at large is entitled to expect, taking all circumstances into account” [11]. Some circumstances might support finding a defect, such as the potential for AI to continuously learn (Proposed PLD, Art. 6(1)(c)) [11], [18]–[19, p. 67]. AI systems that continue to learn after market entry are considered “adaptive.” However, some circumstances might all speak against finding a defect, such as the manufacturer’s loss of control over an adaptive AI system, the manufacturer’s compliance with safety requirements, and potential information about risks provided to end users affecting their expectations (Proposed PLD, Art. 6(1)(e), (f), (h)) [11], [18]–[19, p. 67].

For example, imagine an adaptive AI system trained to read and autonomously report negative X-ray results directly to patients without any review by a human radiologist, while positive X-ray findings by the AI are referred further to a human radiologist for review [18]. Now imagine the AI misses a finger fracture on an X-ray and issues a report of no significant findings. As a result, the X-ray was not reviewed by a radiologist and the patient never received a diagnosis and proper treatment, which led the patient to develop chronic hand pain and numbness. In this case, the AI’s ability to continuously learn might support considering the missed fracture a defect (Proposed PLD, Art. 6(1)(c)), [18]. However, the fact that the AI uses black-box technology to make decisions that cannot be reasonably predicted or prevented by the manufacturer signals a lack of manufacturer control, weighing against finding a defect (Proposed PLD, Art. 6(1)(e)), [11], [18], [see 19, p. 52]. If the manufacturer, in this case, fully complied with the applicable safety requirements and the patient was properly informed of both technical and medical risks regarding the use of the AI, the missed fracture would likely not be seen as a product defect (Proposed PLD, Art. 6(1)(f), (h)), [11], [18], [see 19, p. 52].

Even if the victim of the missed diagnosis is able to obtain both a presumption of defectiveness because the manufacturer failed to disclose required evidence or comply with a safety requirement (Proposed PLD, Art. 9(2)(a)-(b)) [11], [18], and a presumption of causation because the chronic pain and numbness is damage “of a kind typically consistent” with a missed diagnosis (and thus proper treatment) of a finger fracture, the manufacturer might still escape liability under the Proposed PLD (Proposed PLD, Art. 9(3)) [11], [18], [19, pp. 39–40].

Article 10 contains an exemption from liability in the case where the manufacturer could not have discovered the defectiveness under the “objective state of scientific and technical knowledge” (Proposed PLD, Art. 10(1)(e)) [11], [18], [19, pp. 40, 67]. In this case, the black-box nature of the AI’s algorithmic decision-making process might make it impossible for manufacturers to discover that the AI would miss the patient’s finger fracture. This example illustrates how manufacturers of some medical black-box AI technologies might not be liable, even under the Proposed PLD’s new rules [18].

The Proposed AILD seeks to complement the Proposed PLD “to form an overall effective civil liability system” by suggesting fault-based liability rules for damages caused by AI that are not related to defective products [12, Explanatory Memorandum], [19, p. 40]. Like the Proposed PLD, the Proposed AILD also makes some strides toward uniformly addressing liability for AI-caused damage [18]. It does this primarily by reducing evidentiary barriers that claimants will face in fault-based legal actions for AI-caused injury under national law [18]. First, Article 3 enables courts to order third parties and defendants to produce evidence that is “necessary and proportionate” to a claim for AI-caused damage [12], [19, p. 41]. Not complying with this order may create a rebuttable presumption of fault (Proposed AILD, Art. 3(5)) [12], [19, p. 42]. However, the Proposed AILD does not create any new substantive legal duties since fault under the Proposed AILD is still based on the duties of care and breaches thereof as established in national law [12, Explanatory Memorandum], [18]–[19, p. 40]. Second, Article 4 contains a rebuttable presumption that a breach of an existing duty of care by the defendant caused the AI system’s injury-causing output or lack thereof [12], [19, p. 42]. Together, these evidentiary rules address some of the worries about information asymmetry caused by black-box AI by reducing the burden of proof while making evidence more accessible [18]–[19, p. 68].

Unfortunately, the proposed AILD cannot fill the gap in liability for black-box AI technologies that might not be seen as defective under the Proposed PLD because it may be impossible for a claimant to prove that a legally responsible party involved in the development and/or implementation of the AI was at fault [18]. If a black-box AI system causes damage but it was: (1) not defective under the Proposed PLD; and (2) was used by a healthcare organisation and/or provider in compliance with the existing duties of care related to the AI’s implementation and use, it is possible that there is no breach of a duty of care by a legally responsible party under Member State law upon which a claimant could base liability [18]–[19, p. 64].

Consider that the above AI’s failure to recognise the finger fracture as a significant X-ray finding was not, as discussed above, considered a product defect that would trigger liability under the Proposed PLD. In this case, to recover under the Proposed AILD (Art. 2(9)), the patient must first show that a human or legal person breached an existing legal duty [12], [18]. The AI is not a legal person [18]–[19, p. 28]. As a result, the patient must relate the AI’s erroneous finding to the healthcare provider who decided to use the AI [18]–[19, p. 53]. If the healthcare provider’s implementation, oversight, and use of the AI complied with the legal duties - such as following the instructions of the manufacturer,

monitoring the performance of the AI, and adequately training staff using the AI - the healthcare provider will likely not be liable under the Proposed AILD [18]–[19, p. 53].

As a result, it is possible that no breach of a duty of care can be found by a legally responsible party upon which an injured claimant could base liability under the Proposed AILD [18]–[19, p. 64]. While the Proposed AILD’s evidentiary rules might help a claimant understand how the AI’s injury-causing output occurred, a presumption of causation is useless when there is no breach of an existing duty upon which to base liability in the first place [18]. Even assuming such a breach could be identified, the “black box” effect would still make it difficult for a claimant to make the requisite showing that the breach was “reasonably likely” to have “influenced” the AI’s autonomous and opaque medical decision-making (Proposed AILD, Article 4(1)(b)) [18]–[19, p. 42]. In addition, the newly enacted AI Act complicates matters further because it may not be allowed to place such an AI system, as mentioned in the example above, on the market in the future due to the AI Act’s strict requirements for human oversight (Art 26(2) and Art 14(4)) and transparency (Art. 13) [38].

3.1.1.2 Identification of Challenges and Lessons Learned from the EU’s Initiative

The current legal frameworks for liability in both the EU and the US were developed long before the emergence of AI and do not completely address the unique challenges posed by these systems [19, p. 7]. In both jurisdictions, liability for injuries caused by products is governed under product liability law, and liability caused by the fault of a legal person is governed under fault-based law [19, pp. 18–45]. However, injuries caused by AI will not always fit neatly into these existing liability frameworks, and this creates potential liability gaps in both jurisdictions [19, p. 69]. First, manufacturers will likely not be liable unless an AI system is a defective product [18]–[19, pp. 18–20, 33]. It is currently unclear under both the current US and EU frameworks whether and in what circumstances AI might be considered a product [19, pp. 18–19, 33]. If AI is considered a product, it may be difficult to determine when it is defective [19, pp. 18–24, 33]. Second, healthcare providers, both individual and organisational, will likely not be liable unless they were negligent in their implementation and use of the AI [18]–[19, pp. 27–28, 35–36].

We identified a liability gap that emerges primarily in the context of AI models that use deep learning to engage in complex algorithmic reasoning and produce an output [18]–[19, p. 69]. This type of “black-box” AI system is non-interpretable because it is generally impossible for humans to understand the true basis of the AI’s output [18]–[19, pp. 7, 11]. In contrast, transparent and interpretable “white-box” systems allow humans to understand the AI’s reasoning process and assess its output with reasonable effort [18]–[19, pp. 7, 10]. Consequently, it is feasible to trace injuries caused by a white-box AI directly to the actions of healthcare providers and/or manufacturers under the existing liability framework [18]–[19, pp. 7, 10]. If the black-box AI is adaptive and can change after market entry, regulating such adaptive algorithms under the existing liability frameworks becomes even more challenging [18]–[19, pp. 66–67]. It is worth noting that while black-box AI models can be more opaque and less predictable, they can also provide greater accuracy, making them potentially more beneficial in healthcare settings [18]–[19, p. 11]. Finally, we note that when an AI produces an output (i.e., a treatment recommendation) that is reviewed by a human medical provider, the system is generally considered to be non-autonomous [18]–[19, p. 10]. For example, a non-autonomous AI system might provide a treatment recommendation to a physician who acts upon that recommendation to prescribe a certain course of treatment. On the other hand, when an AI system provides an output that a human medical provider does not review, it is generally considered to be “autonomous” [18]–[19, p. 10]. For

example, an autonomous AI system might provide a potential diagnosis directly to a patient based on the patient’s self-described symptoms.

We identified the following common challenges that create a potential gap in the current liability frameworks governing AI-caused injuries in both the EU and US:

- **Challenge 1:** Both jurisdictions need to adjust their legal systems to meet the new demands arising from the rapid development and implementation of AI technology in numerous sectors of society [19, p. 65].
- **Challenge 2:** In both jurisdictions, claimants may encounter challenges in linking AI-caused injuries to human fault, making it difficult to hold a human party legally accountable under the current liability framework [19, p. 65].
- **Challenge 3:** AI-driven technologies do not always function like traditional products, making existing product liability rules a poor fit for some cases involving AI-driven medical “products” [19, p. 66].
- **Challenge 4:** In both jurisdictions, patients may find it challenging to obtain evidence and meet evidentiary burdens in certain cases involving an AI-caused injury [19, p. 67].

3.1.2 Liability Considerations for AI in Healthcare

We analysed developments involving the regulation and liability of AI for medical or health purposes, including a case study of AI-driven technology in gastroenterology (Section 3.1.2.1), the potential risks posed by GenAI in the health sector (Section 3.1.2.2), liability implications that arise in the context of sharing patient data for AI development (Section 3.1.2.3), and specific issues that might affect liability for surgeons who use AI-driven tools (Section 3.1.2.4).

3.1.2.1 Examination of Liability in Use Case for AI-Driven Technology in Gastroenterology

We examined use cases to explore potential liability for implementing AI-driven technologies with varying levels of automation in gastroenterology practice. Our research results were reported in: Artificial Intelligence and Medical Liability in Gastrointestinal Endoscopy in *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology* [40].

AI-driven tools are already being used in gastrointestinal endoscopy practice. AI computer-aided detection (CADe) that helps physicians detect colorectal polyps is already on the market [40, p. 1165]. Additionally, new AI-driven tools like computer-aided diagnosis (CADx), which could assist with polyp diagnosis, and automated capsule endoscopy (ACE), which could review and interpret capsule endoscopy images, are on the horizon [40, pp. 1165–1166]. Notably, AI-driven CADx and ACE involve higher levels of automation, with ACE potentially capable of fully autonomous capsule endoscopy reporting [40, p. 1166]. We examined potential liability for physicians using AI-driven tools in gastrointestinal endoscopy practice under the US fault-based liability framework [40, pp. 1166–1167]. For a physician to be at fault for patient injuries arising from their use of AI-driven tools, they must first breach the duty of care owed to their patients [40, p. 1167]. Second, this breach must cause the patient to suffer an injury [40, p. 1167].

For AI-driven tools for endoscopy, the standard of care that the physician owes to patients must be established by an expert in the field of endoscopy and will be heavily influenced by the applicable clinical practice guidelines and evidence-based standards developed in the medical profession and published in common physician reference tools [40, p. 1167]. Additionally, whether AI-driven tools are

regulated, legally marketed, demanded by patients, and covered by insurers can influence whether they are accepted by the medical profession as part of the standard of care [40, p. 1167]. Even if AI-driven tools for endoscopy are accepted as part of the standard of care for gastrointestinal endoscopy, physicians and healthcare organisations that use these tools might still be liable if they violate more general standards of care by failing to properly implement them into clinical practice [40, p. 1167]. This includes ensuring that the tools are used to treat the right patient population, that they are used in accordance with manufacturers' instructions, that they are correctly maintained and updated, that medical staff are trained on how to use them, and that patients are appropriately informed about their risks [40, p. 1167].

If either the individual clinician or the healthcare organisation using the AI-driven endoscopy tools breaches the standard of care, they will be liable to the patient if that breach caused the patient's injury [40, pp. 1167–1168]. Causation is often challenging to prove in medical negligence cases because it can be hard to distinguish whether their injury was caused by the healthcare provider's breach versus the patient's pre-existing medical condition [40, p. 1168]. We note, however, that in the US, if a healthcare provider's breach increases the risk of injury for a patient's medical treatment, and an injury manifests from that increased risk, causation might be satisfied, and the healthcare provider can still be liable [40, p. 1168].

Our examination of liability in the case of AI-driven gastrointestinal endoscopy tools highlighted the importance of clear clinical guidelines generally relating to the accepted use of such tools in clinical practice and, more specifically, to the level of physician oversight required for tools considering their level of autonomy [40, p. 1168]. We also concluded that physicians should clearly document reasons for either relying on or ignoring recommendations made by AI-driven tools [40, p. 1168].

3.1.2.2 Examination of Risks Introduced by Generative AI in Healthcare

We also examined liability concerns and safety risks associated with the new development of generative AI (GenAI) and its increasing use by healthcare providers and patients. Our results from this research were published in the following publication: *Generative AI in Health Care and Liability Risks for Physicians and Safety Concerns for Patients in JAMA* [41]. We also examined privacy risks introduced by GenAI, focusing on the GenAI data lifecycle and data privacy frameworks in the EU and the US. Our research results were published in the following publication: *Privacy of Personal Data in the Generative AI Data Lifecycle in NYU Journal of Intellectual Property & Entertainment Law* [42].

The rapid development of GenAI, like OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini, impacts the way in which patients and healthcare providers obtain information related to health and medical treatment [41, p. 313]. GenAI describes a type of AI that is capable of producing new content, like text, images, and sounds [41, p. 313]. Large language models (LLMs) enable GenAI applications to mimic human-generated text [41, p. 313]. LLMs that provide health information are generally "black boxes," because users cannot understand exactly how or why the AI chose to generate a specific text [41, p. 313]. As a result, there are liability implications for healthcare providers and patients who use GenAI to produce health information [41, pp. 313–314]. GenAI models like ChatGPT are "general-use AI" that are available to the general public to answer questions on various topics but do not currently undergo regulatory review, by regulators like the FDA, because they are not presently considered medical devices [41, p. 313], [19, p. 6]. Additionally, GenAI can provide false information with a high level of

confidence (referred to as “hallucinations”) in response to providers’ and patients’ inquiries [41, p. 313], [19, pp. 7, 15–16].

Healthcare providers may face liability when they rely on GenAI outputs for treatment decisions [41, pp. 313–314]. This is because it may be impossible for the provider to independently evaluate the accuracy of the AI’s output, thus limiting their ability to exercise medical judgment in clinical decisions that rely on information generated by the AI [41, pp. 313–314]. In contrast to other medical technologies that rely on white-box AI models (e.g., a decision tree that assesses stroke risk) or well-established scientific principles (e.g., Covid tests that detect the presence of a virus), physicians may not be able to provide meaningful expert medical oversight or review of the content produced by a GenAI model [41, p. 313], [18].

As a result, while physicians are typically viewed as the ultimate medical decision-makers, their inability to understand how GenAI generates information used in patient treatment means that their perceived control may actually be limited by their black-box nature [41, p. 313], [18]. The current law regarding reliance on medical information generated by an AI is unclear, but whether providers are held responsible for patient injuries caused by the use of GenAI depends on the applicable standard of care [19, p. 196]. Currently, the standard of care likely does not include the use of GenAI to treat patients, and a healthcare provider’s reliance on information provided by GenAI could lead to liability [41, pp. 313–314], [19, pp. 27–30].

Patients who rely on GenAI to obtain health information may unwittingly make decisions that are not in their best interest or that could even be harmful [41, p. 314]. This is because, unlike healthcare providers, patients typically lack the medical expertise required to evaluate the validity of the information generated by the AI and the potential health implications of following such advice [41, p. 314]. Currently, if a patient suffers harm as a result of following medical advice generated by a direct-to-consumer GenAI system, it may be challenging to determine who is at fault and who bears the responsibility for the patient’s injuries [41, p. 314]. For example, the AI company might claim that patients are warned that the GenAI system might produce false information and warned against relying on health information produced by GenAI.

Given the current state of uncertainty in the regulatory and liability frameworks about GenAI, it is crucial that healthcare providers and patients remain sceptical of health information provided by GenAI [41, p. 314]. It is also important for medical professional associations to provide guidance to both patients and physicians regarding the risks of using GenAI in healthcare [41, p. 314].

3.1.2.3 Liability Implications for Sharing Patients’ Data for AI Development

We examined liability issues associated with sharing patients’ health data for the purpose of developing AI-driven medical technologies in the US context. Our results from this research were published in the following publication: Health Care AI and Patient Privacy—*Dinerstein v Google* in *JAMA* [43].

In the US, a case involving liability for sharing patient health data for AI development raised several implications for healthcare organisations that collect and share patient data for the purpose of developing AI-driven technologies [43, p. 909]. Ultimately, a US federal court of appeals dismissed a patient’s claim that the hospital’s sharing his allegedly “de-identified” medical records with Google for medical AI development violated his privacy and property rights [43, p. 909]–[44].

The data sharing in question occurred when the University of Chicago and its medical centre (UC) entered into a research partnership with Google and shared patient data with Google to facilitate the development of “an AI model that could predict significant medical events and reduce hospital readmissions,” using “de-identified” data of the hospital’s patients, including those of the plaintiff in this case [43, p. 909]–[44].

The plaintiff, in this case, filed a complaint in federal district court claiming that the collection and use of his health data for AI development violated his privacy rights and constituted a breach of contract [43, p. 909], [45]. First, the plaintiff claimed that sharing his “de-identified” medical records with Google violated his privacy because the records could potentially be re-identified by Google by combining the shared data, which included dates of service and free-text medical notes, with other data that Google had, including geolocation data from Google Maps [43, p. 909], [45]. Notably, pursuant to the research agreement between UC and Google, Google agreed that it would not attempt to re-identify any of the patients and, in fact, made no such attempts to identify this plaintiff in the course of the research [43, p. 910]–[44].

The court of first instance, here the US federal district court, dismissed the privacy claim. The court found that Illinois, which governed this case, is unlikely to recognise a legal claim based upon a breach of medical confidentiality [43, p. 909], [46].

Second, the plaintiff claimed that UC breached its contract, which he signed on admission [43, p. 909], [46]. The plaintiff received on admission not only a privacy notice but also signed an agreement outlining that his medical data might be used for research, that he would not be entitled to compensation stemming from such use, and that UC would comply with the US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and other federal and state laws, and make all efforts to preserve his privacy [43, p. 909]–[44], [46].

The district court found (1) that the records did include protected health information (PHI) under HIPAA; and (2) that sharing the plaintiff’s health information, including the dates of his admission, violated HIPAA’s ban on selling PHI without written authorisation (45 CFR §164.502(a)(5)(ii) & §164.508(a)(4)) [43, p. 909], [46]. The court noted that the promise to provide UC with a perpetual license to use the AI model once developed was a type of compensation that classified UC’s sharing of health data as a sale and required the plaintiff’s written authorisation that he never gave [43, p. 909], [46]. Although HIPAA itself does not give a patient a right to sue for a violation of the federal statute itself, the court noted that UC’s promise in its *own* contract was more than just its obligations under HIPAA and gave the plaintiff the right to sue for breach of contract under state law [43, p. 909], [46]. Nevertheless, the district court dismissed the breach of contract claim, finding that the plaintiff did not suffer damages [43, p. 909], [46].

The plaintiff appealed to the Seventh Circuit Court of Appeals, which confirmed the district court’s dismissal of the case [43, p. 910]–[44]. Notably, the court of appeals found that the plaintiff did neither have a valid legal privacy claim nor a contract claim because he did not suffer any harm [43, p. 910]–[44]. The court noted that in order to file a lawsuit in federal court, the plaintiff must suffer the type of harm that is both concrete (not abstract) and imminent (not speculative) [43, p. 910]–[44].

The court of appeals noted about the plaintiff’s privacy claim that Google agreed not to re-identify patients, had not re-identified the plaintiff, and that the risk of future re-identification (using Google’s geolocation data and the dates of service) was too abstract [43, p. 910]–[44]. Further, it found that

even if there was a breach of contract, a breach alone, without a concrete and imminent injury, was not enough to form a valid legal claim [43, p. 910]–[44]. Here, the court relied on two main points. First, it found that the plaintiff did not suffer monetary harm largely because he does not have a property right in his medical information [43, p. 910]–[44]. Second, it noted that even if UC benefited from disclosing patients’ medical records by getting a perpetual license to use the AI developed by Google during the research project, the plaintiff did not suffer a loss, and thus did not incur the requisite harm to file a lawsuit [43, p. 910]–[44].

Interestingly, while the court of appeals cast doubt on whether the plaintiff’s medical records could truly be re-identified, it did not assess whether the medical records were PHI under HIPAA or whether the sharing of these records with Google constituted a HIPAA violation and if so, whether such violation could support the plaintiff’s breach of contract claim [43, p. 910]–[44]. The district court’s findings on these issues are now overtaken by the court of appeals’ decision dismissing the case because the plaintiff did not suffer the kind of harm necessary to give him a valid legal claim [43, p. 910]–[44], [46].

Courts will continue to encounter cases that concern health data and medical AI research and development [43, p. 910]. While some claims in the US might fail because patients do not have a property interest in personal information, and it is challenging or impossible to show “harm” necessary for a valid legal claim, others may succeed if they are in a jurisdiction that recognises claims specifically concerning medical confidentiality [43, p. 910]. For now, US federal law alone does not give private citizens the right to file lawsuits against entities that share their health information for research or even commercial purposes [43, p. 909]. Still, healthcare providers involved in medical AI research and development are responsible for complying with ethical, administrative, and regulatory rules [43, p. 910]. As a result, they should strive, as always, to protect patient confidentiality and ensure transparency surrounding their use of patients’ health information [43, p. 910]. This can mean reviewing and updating disclosure and privacy practices to keep up to date with the rapidly progressing AI technology [43, p. 910].

3.1.2.4 Identification of Liability Issues Specific to Surgeons

We conducted interdisciplinary research to discover potential legal issues that impact the use of AI-driven technology for surgeons specifically.

We examined the question of whether surgical video recordings and the related metadata (surgical video data) that is collected in connection with AI-driven technologies in surgery should be included in patients’ medical records. Our results from this research were published in the following publication: Surgical Video Data: “In,” “Out,” or “Shake It All About” the Medical Record in *Annals of Surgery* [47].

The use of AI-driven technologies in surgery often includes the collection of surgical video data; however, there is not much discussion about the impact of including such data in patients’ medical records. We provided an overview of the risks and benefits of including surgical video data in patients’ medical records and urged healthcare providers to carefully consider reasons for including or excluding some or all of a patient’s medical video data in their medical records [47, pp. 382–383].

One important consideration for including surgical video data in patients’ medical records is the potential health benefits of giving patients access to surgical video data, which might include useful insights for their medical treatment [47, p. 382]. Another potential benefit to the wholesale inclusion of surgical video data in medical records is that it can eliminate legal uncertainty surrounding both patients’ privacy and their rights to access this data [47, p. 382].

On the other hand, we noted some disadvantages to including surgical video data in patients' medical records that stem from the risks of giving patients access to data that can impact the privacy of third parties and the confidentiality of information needed to improve healthcare quality management at the organisational level [47, pp. 382–383]. This could discourage both surgeons and healthcare organisations from using surgical video data for training, performance evaluation, quality control, and risk management, which ultimately ensure the benefit of all patients generally [47, p. 383].

From a liability perspective, we noted that, on the one hand, including surgical video data in patients' medical records might exonerate surgeons who followed the relevant standards of care in cases of undesired surgical outcomes [47, p. 382]. On the other hand, patient access to surgical video data might subject surgeons to increased liability because patients and their attorneys might be hyper-critical of the surgical performance depicted in the video without having the expertise to understand the surgical process [47, pp. 382–383].

We also examined the options of including some surgical video data in the patients' medical records while excluding others [47, p. 383]. Although this demands a more nuanced approach to the decision of whether to include or exclude surgical video data in patients' medical records, we highlight that it might also provide a balance by including only the surgical video data that is relevant to the patient's medical treatment while excluding other data that is only relevant for quality assessment and improvement [47, p. 383].

We also examined surgery-specific benefits and the legal implications of using AI-driven technologies to produce real-time recommendations in surgery. Our results from this research were published in the following publication: The AI-enhanced Surgeon - Integrating Black-box Artificial Intelligence in the Operating Room in *International Journal of Surgery* [48].

AI-driven technologies are already being used in pathology and radiology for screening imagery for human validation [48]. Additionally, AI-driven tools are assisting healthcare providers with administrative tasks such as documentation and prescribing [48]. For surgeons, new advances in computer vision also enable AI-driven tools to help surgeons gain anatomical, pathological, and physiological insights and direction during an operation [48]. Robotic systems are also used in surgery to perform parts of procedures [48]. Beyond the current technology that provides surgeons with either manual task assistance or enhanced information that must still be interpreted by the surgeon, AI-driven surgical decision-making can help them make better decisions in real time [48]. However, the integration of AI-driven decision support into surgery has important liability implications, particularly when the AI is a non-interpretable black-box system, and surgeons cannot understand the actual basis underlying the AI's decision recommendation [48].

While the basis for recommendations by interpretable white-box models is transparent, non-interpretable black-box models often provide more accurate recommendations, making them potentially more valuable in the operating room, where surgeons must make many instantaneous and often irreversible decisions [48]. The frameworks for AI regulation are currently in flux, but regulators often promote black-box AI models that are explainable [48]. It is important to recognise that explainability does not provide the true reason underlying the AI's output, but instead, refers to a post-hoc explanation provided by a second white-box algorithm that approximates a likely explanation for the output, which may not be correct [8], [19, p. 12]. Instead, a more dynamic approach, which focuses on reliability, rather than explainability, might encourage the development and adoption of beneficial AI-driven tools in surgery [48]. Manufacturers of black-box AI-driven surgical technology should aim to

develop systems that provide surgeons with both assumptions that the system makes as well as any medically relevant information that relates to the AI's output. This type of post-hoc transparency will be beneficial for surgeons, who can then use this information to better evaluate the AI's recommendation using their medical expertise [48].

In terms of liability, for black-box AI-driven technologies in surgery, again, this will rely heavily on whether the use of such technologies is incorporated into the standard of care for the relevant surgical expertise [48]. We again note that the premarket regulation and surgeons' trust in such technologies can impact their uptake and ultimate integration into these standards of care [48]. Ideally, a fair liability system for using AI-driven technologies in surgery would consider more than the surgeon's individual actions, but also the manufacturer's design and validation of the AI and the hospital's integration of AI into its surgical practice [48].

3.2 Empirical Legal Research on Surgeons' Perspectives on Liability

As medical AI becomes more prevalent in healthcare, challenges regarding legal liability persist. We carried out a focus group study with surgeons in the EU and the US to discover their perspectives on liability for using AI-driven technology in surgery. These perspectives are crucial for understanding how surgeons view liability currently, how they perceive liability risks for AI-driven technologies, and what they consider necessary for mitigating these risks. This study helped us tackle challenges we discovered in our normative legal research into the liability framework in a manner that considers the domain expertise of surgeons themselves. This was the first empirical research study that investigated surgeons' perspectives on liability for AI-driven technology in surgery and included both EU and US surgeons as study participants. Our methods and results from this research are summarised below and were published in the following publication: Surgeons' Perspectives on Liability for the Use of Artificial Intelligence Technologies in the United States and European Union: Results From a Focus Group Study in *Annals of Surgery Open* [17].

Our focus group study included 18 total surgeon participants, which included 11 EU surgeons and 7 US surgeons [17]. Each surgeon participated in one of six total focus groups. Three focus groups were comprised of EU surgeons, and three focus groups were comprised of US surgeons [17, see especially Table 1 (focus group participants' description) and Supplemental Material 1 (focus group guide)]. The participants were asked optional anonymous demographic questions, but not all participants chose to answer them [17, Table 1 (focus group participants' description)]. According to such answers, the following demographic information was reported: (1) gender identity: man (n = 13) and woman (n = 4); (2) age group: 26–35 years old (n = 7), 36–45 years old (n = 4), 46–55 years old (n = 3), 56–65 years old (n = 1), 66–75 years old (n = 2); (3) race, nationality, and ethnicity: Asian (n = 3); Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish (n = 2); Middle Eastern or North African (n = 2); White (n = 12) [17, Table 1 (focus group participants' description)].

An analysis of the validated and anonymised focus group transcripts revealed five main themes, which we reported as follows:

“(1) acknowledgment of the potential benefits of using AI-driven technology in surgery, (2) acceptance of surgeon responsibility, (3) recognition that AI may impact the standard of care, (4) scepticism about potential liability for AI manufacturers, and (5) the importance of patient information and consent” [17, for more information on the methods, particularly data collection and analysis, see already Section 2.2 above].

We also identified subthemes relating to the reliability of AI-driven technologies in surgery and the role of regulation of such technology [17]. Additionally, across all discussion themes, participants utilised analogies to convey their viewpoints on liability for AI-driven technologies [17].

When discussing the potential impact of AI-driven technologies in surgery, participants identified potential benefits relating to improved patient outcomes, enhanced surgical quality, and reduced administrative burdens [17].

Participant 2 of Focus Group 4 (US):

I think, on the patient's health,... it certainly has the potential to decrease operative time or, in some cases, even prevent a re-operation by helping identify some aspect of either anatomy or the overall mechanism of disease, and that will hopefully decrease length of stays and hospital admission times [17].

The participants all readily accepted that surgeons should be ultimately responsible for their patients, and they highlighted both the complexity of surgical decision-making as well as the importance of the surgeon's expertise and experience [17].

Regarding the impact of AI-driven technologies on the standard of care for surgeons, participants generally believed that AI was not currently incorporated into the standard of care, but they discussed how AI could change the standard of care for surgeons in the future [17]. Participants discussed how if AI becomes part of the standard of care in the future, it will be important for the surgeon to document reasons for relying or not relying on the AI's recommendation, with reference to the current role of clinical guidelines, which they emphasised are not mandatory but rather reflect the current state of surgical practice [17].

Participant 4 of Focus Group 2 (EU):

But I mean, I think, that at the end of it, the standard of care will change, and will adapt to this new tool. It's not now, maybe not even... in the next 10 years, but still,... it will happen in the end [17].

With regard to liability for manufacturers of AI-driven technologies, participants were not confident that manufacturers would share liability for injuries caused by these technologies [17]. They recognised, however, that a clear malfunction of an AI system would likely lead to manufacturer liability [17]. Despite viewing the surgeons as the primarily responsible party, they discussed the unfairness of completely absolving manufacturers of liability for patient injuries when surgeons followed the instructions of the manufacturer for using AI-driven technologies [17].

Participant 3 of Focus Group 3 (EU):

... liability remains surgeon's problem. Unfortunately [17].

Participant 1 of Focus Group 1 (EU):

... I would like to have a balance on this, at least a balance. But if I really do everything that the artificial intelligence machine say to me that is correct and is the best for the patient, I technically cannot be responsible for anything that should happen because I follow completely the rule [17].

Participants often discussed how undesirable surgical outcomes are often caused by risks inherent in surgical treatment [17]. They discussed the importance of the consent process in future surgeries involving AI-driven technologies and indicated that the level of information provided to the patient about the risks associated with using AI-driven technologies could factor into liability determination [17].

Participant 1 of Focus Group 6 (US):

... the patients should be involved in this decision making, if he or she will accept the decision of the machine [17].

Participants generally agreed that the reliability of AI-driven technologies was important for acceptance by surgeons [17]. Reliability for them included understanding the general principles, evidence, and data underlying the development, training, and validation of the AI [17]. They were less concerned with grasping the purely technical aspects of how deep-learning AI technologies arrived at a particular recommendation [17].

Participant 3 of Focus Group 1 (EU):

... it's impossible for us surgeons to understand the basis of a machine, I mean, AI system, and for me that the most important thing is on which data is build the AI [17].

There was some discussion about regulators' role in ensuring that AI-driven technologies on the market are reliable [17]. While there was no overall agreement on the trustworthiness of the regulatory process, EU participants appeared more willing to trust AI technologies that underwent regulatory review than the US participants [17].

Participant 2 of Focus Group 1 (EU):

I think if the AI system was approved, and the surgeon agreed to use it, so the surgeon is obliged to use it [17].

Participant 2 of Focus Group 4 (US):

I mean the green light just means that I would be willing to at least pitch it to my patients. If the tool is still in the experimental phase where no regulatory body has looked at it or approved it, then my skepticism and hesitancy to even pitch it or use it would be significantly higher, right [17]?

Finally, participants conceptualised the integration of AI-driven technologies in surgery using a wide range of analogies, ranging from medications to CT scans to staplers [17, Supplemental Material 2]. This is not surprising since the emergence and adoption of new technologies often involve comparisons with better-understood technologies already in use [17].

The construction of analogies allows for extrapolation of the various characteristics and possible implications of new technology, but these comparisons can also restrict adoption by framing emerging technologies in specific ways [17]. For instance, the participants compared AI-driven technologies to CT and EKG scans, fluorescence, and energy devices, noting that while these technologies do not ensure 100% effectiveness or accuracy, they are utilised because they provide certain benefits to patients and support clinicians despite the associated risks [17, see also Supplemental Material 2 (summary of analogies)]. When discussing their use of AI-driven technologies in surgery, they typically used the term "tool" to describe the role of these technologies [17]. Some study participants compared

the use of AI-driven technology in surgery to dye, the assistance of trainees, or using autopilot on a plane [17]. Additionally, some study participants downplayed the possible role of AI-driven technologies by likening them to staplers, guns, cars, and laparoscopic robotic instruments [17]. Generally, study participants could not envision AI-driven technologies as anything more than either informational tools (i.e., those assisting in surgical decision-making) or functional tools (i.e., those supporting surgical technique) [17]. This discussion echoed participants' general opinions that surgeons themselves, even with the use of AI-driven technologies, were the ultimate decision makers and thus remained primarily responsible for the patient [17].

On the other hand, surgeons recognised that future AI-driven technologies may require a different balance of responsibility because AI will become more complex [17]. A different balance may be useful, for instance, in situations where AI differs from a traditional medical device, as it surpasses a surgeon's performance on specific tasks, or where it contrasts with traditional medication, as it continuously adapts to new data [17]. Notably, the analogies used by study participants emerged throughout all major themes and seemed to influence their perspectives on liability in general [17].

The regulatory framework for AI-driven technologies in surgery is still in flux in both the EU and the US, which raises important questions regarding whether regulators will be able to ensure that these technologies are safe and reliable [17]. The focus group study revealed important factors likely to impact liability for the use of AI-driven technologies in surgery, including: (1) the ability of surgeons to understand the principles underlying the AI development and training process; (2) the level of information regarding the functionality, intended uses, and limitations of the AI; and (3) the role of regulators in ensuring that AI-driven technologies are safe and reliable [17]. Providing clear information to surgeons about these aspects of AI development and marketing will help them better understand the role of various AI-driven technologies and the liability risks associated with their use [17].

Of course, our study is not without limitations [17]. Recruiting surgeons, a highly specialised group with demanding schedules, has proven to be challenging [17]. On one hand, the small number of focus groups and the number of participants in each group may have reduced the diversity and depth of perspectives [17]. On the other hand, the expert status of the participants also strengthened our study, as it provides insights into an important topic from experts [17]. Additionally, recent research indicates that three focus groups are sufficient to detect the most prevalent themes [17], [49]. In our focus group study, the meetings facilitated dynamic interaction and lively discussions among participants, and the generated data achieved saturation for identifying five themes [17].

4 Impact and Conclusion

4.1 Impact

4.1.1 *Impact on Liability Frameworks Governing the Use of AI-Driven Technologies in Surgery*

Our research revealed several gaps in the legal liability systems concerning injuries caused by AI technology in general and medical AI technology in particular. We identified several similarities and differences in the jurisdictions' approaches to AI liability and their efforts (or lack thereof) to address the liability challenges posed by AI, including those that will arise within the medical liability systems. We identified potential risks that certain AI-driven medical technologies pose to patient safety by

revealing potential gaps in the existing liability frameworks. Our analysis of the regulatory and liability framework can influence the development and adoption of beneficial AI technologies.

Our research also revealed surgeons’ views on liability regarding the use of AI-driven technology in surgery. These perspectives influence ongoing legal research aimed at developing fair and suitable legal regulatory and liability frameworks, both of which are in flux in the EU and the US. This analysis identified potential benefits for surgeons utilising AI-driven technologies in surgery, including insights that permit personalised treatment, enhance surgeon performance, improve patient outcomes, and increase access to medical care.

4.1.2 Impact on Standards of Care for Using AI-driven Technologies in Surgery

We also gained insights into the liability issues surrounding the standard of care for using AI-driven technologies. Because liability under the EU and US frameworks for physicians using AI in medicine is unsettled, physicians in both jurisdictions face questions when deciding to adopt a particular AI technology. We believe that these challenges create uncertainty for both physicians and patients. For physicians, it is not always clear whether using AI will subject them to a new or different liability risk than they would encounter if they chose not to use it. For patients, it may be difficult to connect the AI to the specific injury or to obtain sufficient evidence to meet legal requirements. Moreover, we believe these risks and uncertainties can vary depending on what type of AI is used. Generative AI models, for example, pose challenges different from white-box AI [41], [18]. While physicians may be able to provide meaningful oversight in the latter, they may be unable to do so in the former. We believe this oversight responsibility, along with the technological differences, can affect physicians’ legal obligations and hence their liability risk [41], [18]–[19]. In either case, however, using AI as part of clinical care could increase the physician’s risk of liability because the standard of care often lags behind technology [19].

4.1.3 Impact of Liability as a Potential Barrier to Adoption of AI-Driven Technologies in Surgery

We believe that accuracy and evidence of success will be the most important factors in the adoption of AI-driven technologies in surgery. While transparency will remain crucial, there is likely to be some tolerance for “black boxes” as long as surgeons know that the AI operates as promised (e.g., through the completion of clinical trials) and receive all medically relevant information regarding the AI’s output (e.g., how the AI weighs its recommendations or the assumptions it makes) [48]. In other words, it is likely unnecessary for every computational step to be traceable [48].

4.1.4 Impact of Regulation on Liability for AI-Driven Technologies in Surgery

Surgery is a high-risk clinical environment. Consequently, liability risks in surgery are often more pronounced than in standard clinical settings. Yet, regulation can influence how much of the risk manufacturers and physicians actually bear. In the US, for example, the regulatory pathway through which a medical device reaches the market affects the success of claims by injured patients. Manufacturers that reach the market through the most rigorous pathway (so-called Premarket Approval or PMA) have greater liability protection than those that go through a less rigorous pathway (so-called Premarket Notification or 510(k) clearance) [21]. While the former typically requires clinical trial data, the latter reaches the market primarily by demonstrating the medical device is “substantially equivalent” to a legally marketed device (so-called “predicate device”) [21]. Complicating this framework is another pathway to market—De Novo Classification Request—that often includes but

does not necessarily require clinical evidence [21]. As discussed in more detail above in Section 3.1.1.1.3.1, manufacturers with PMA devices have greater liability protection and may successfully bring the defence of express pre-emption [21]. In contrast, such defence is not available for manufacturers of 510(k) devices [21]. However, it is currently unclear whether it is available for manufacturers of De Novo devices, and hardly any courts have addressed this question [21], [34]–[35]. The answer to this question is particularly important for AI-enabled devices, which reach the market through the De Novo pathway at nearly three times the rate of non-AI-enabled devices [21].

While this regulatory landscape has direct implications for manufacturers, it can also affect clinicians and hospitals. When liability protections are greater for manufacturers, hospitals and physicians become bigger targets for malpractice claims. If the AI technology is not properly validated or does not meet the standard of care, then physicians and hospitals may be taking a greater risk than manufacturers in deploying the AI in clinical settings. In such cases, physicians and hospitals may need to address these risks with insurers or negotiate indemnification agreements with manufacturers. Regardless of how the risks are resolved, the regulatory landscape has significant implications for manufacturers and users of AI technology, as well as patients.

4.1.5 Impact of Broader Aspects of AI Regulation and Liability on AI-Driven Technologies in Surgery

Since the development of AI-driven technologies in surgery does not occur in isolation but is part of the broader trend of technological advancements in AI and medicine, our research included an analysis of legal liability for the development and use of AI in this wider context. This interdisciplinary research enabled us to identify liability issues related to the development and use of AI-driven technologies in surgery, which arise from cross-sector risks and regulation of AI more generally. In particular, it is essential to understand that surgery is not a precise science, and surgeons are not mere statisticians [48]. The determination of a surgeon's liability for a patient's surgical injury hinges on evaluating whether the surgeon's performance meets the standard of care, taking into account the widely accepted practices for surgeons in comparable situations, independent of the ultimate surgical results [48].

4.1.6 Stakeholder Conference

Many different stakeholders use AI-driven technologies in surgery, all with different but important perspectives. Gathering, listening, and discussing the myriad issues confronted by stakeholders is crucial to understanding the directions AI-driven technologies are taking in healthcare and to furthering the research of the CLASSICA project. To attract a wide range of high-profile, high-impact speakers, we partnered with C5 Communications to host a stakeholder conference (*Life Sciences AI Summit – Europe*) in Brussels, Belgium [50]. The stakeholders and speakers included prominent individuals, such as those from academia, industry, and government. For example, we had speakers from the EU Commission, the OECD, Novo Nordisk, Microsoft, Thermo Fisher Scientific, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, the German Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices, Covington & Burling, Axon Lawyers, and a variety of others.

Leveraging the expertise of these speakers, the agenda of the stakeholder conference covered a wide range of issues affecting AI-driven technologies in healthcare, including balancing privacy with innovation, the EU AI Act, the use of AI in clinical trials and drug discovery, jurisdictional differences in regulation, public-private partnerships, and ensuring equity, equality, and fairness when using AI technologies [50, see agenda].

The conference took place over two full days in March 2025 and generated significant insights. For example, one of the presenters from the European Commission explained the overall approach of the new EU AI Act and the reasons for it. His presentation spawned discussion among the stakeholders—including those at Microsoft, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, and Elekta—about how best to approach the new regulatory question for AI in the EU. The discussants explored the ways in which AI regulation has shaped their approach to technological innovation in the medical space and how it is likely to do so in the future.

The conference explored other issues in detail, as well. Lawyers and industry leaders explored how the GDPR can influence the development of AI-enabled products. And representatives from leading law firms and drug manufacturers explained how AI had altered the clinical trial landscape. Academics and regulators described the regulatory pathways and strategic considerations firms should be aware of in developing medical AI. Other panels with financial professionals, scientists, and economists discussed investment considerations in the context of private equity and public-private partnerships to promote AI development. Each panel shared unique information about the different considerations and funding models for AI-enabled innovations and how to ensure developments proceed equitably and fairly.

Speakers and participants also discussed legal aspects associated with AI, including risks. For example, Lawyers from leading intellectual property law firms and academic institutions discussed how to evaluate risks before and after commercialisation, including risks of intellectual property infringement. Among the risks discussed were the potential for copyright infringement during training and output of AI models, as well as the protectability of AI models under patent law. One of the CLASSICA PIs, Timo Minssen (UCPH), spoke in the panel on intellectual property protections about how patent law treats inventions created in whole or part with AI, as well as the changes regulators might need to ensure that patent law can encourage AI innovation. CLASSICA PI Sara Gerke (UIUC) presented in the panel about the power of AI in medical device and diagnostic advancement and drug discovery. In particular, she provided a comprehensive overview of the regulation of AI-enabled medical devices in the US and the challenges that regulators, such as the FDA, face throughout the AI lifecycles, including comparisons with the EU.

The CLASSICA team was further highlighted at the Life Sciences AI Summit by presenting our recent findings in a CLASSICA-dedicated panel. The CLASSICA team discussed the medical experience of the clinical trial in the surgery room (UCD), as well as how it trained and used AI during the surgery (Arctur). It also shared results from the legal analysis, highlighting how data privacy and liability laws apply to the CLASSICA tool, both in the EU and in the US (UCPH and UIUC). The team fielded questions from the audience and received helpful comments about new potential strategies for successful clinical translation of the AI tool.

Finally, various stakeholders discussed how AI is transforming healthcare delivery more broadly. Discussions ranged from using AI for patient monitoring and recordkeeping to using AI software as a medical device. Significant attention was given to how AI can be integrated into clinical decision-making throughout the healthcare system and the potential regulatory challenges to doing so. The stakeholder conference concluded with a rich exchange about how to use AI ethically and sustainably.

4.2 Conclusion

The main goal of Task 8.3 was to analyse the current legal landscape and new developments in the EU and the US related to liability for the use of AI-assisted or autonomous medical tools. We used mixed

methods analysis to answer key questions related to liability, data privacy, and ethics of using these tools. Some of this work was legal, describing the existing legal frameworks that governed medical AI and the unresolved issues and gaps those frameworks presented. Other aspects of this work were empirical, in particular, conducting a focus group study to better understand EU and US surgeons' perspectives on liability for the use of AI technologies.¹ An overarching feature of this work was its interdisciplinary nature, drawing on a team of experts that ranged from medicine to law and ethics. One key finding is that the liability landscape is still unsettled, even in jurisdictions like the EU that have adopted AI-specific legislation. Task 8.3 concluded that identifying areas of uncertainty depended on a variety of factors, including the type of AI technology, the applicable standard of care, and the regulatory controls that apply.

Box 1. Questions Addressed in Task 8.3

1. Who may be held liable under current law if an AI-supported operation goes wrong: the surgeon, the hospital, or the AI manufacturer?

- The surgeon may be liable if their use of the AI-enabled technology does not meet the standard of care.
- The hospital may be liable for the surgeon's actions or for not validating the tool.
- The manufacturer may be liable if its product is defectively manufactured, designed, or marketed.

2. What are surgeons' perspectives on liability for using AI-supported surgical tools?

- Surgeons understand the potential benefits of AI-driven technology, including reduced paperwork and increased surgical outcomes.
- Surgeons have concerns about the reliability of AI technologies and seek clarity on the model's training process, as well as the data and evidence used to create the AI.
- Surgeons typically accept their responsibility for their patients.
- Surgeons currently do not consider AI as part of the standard of care, though they recognise this may change in the future.
- Surgeons appreciate their responsibility to act ethically, including in obtaining informed consent.
- Surgeons expressed dissatisfaction with the prospect of being liable when following manufacturer instructions for the use of the AI-enabled technology.
- Trust in regulators varies among surgeons across different jurisdictions.

3. What steps can individual and organisational healthcare providers take to avoid potential litigation in AI-supported operations?

- Develop robust disclosure, security, and consent workflows that adequately inform patients of the use of AI and the protection of their data and comply with applicable data privacy laws.
- Ensure proper validation and monitoring of AI technology and develop clear practice guidelines for the use of AI in the clinical setting.
- Train physicians on the proper use of AI technology, including the ability to understand or rely on an output.

¹ Focus Group Study.

- Use indemnification agreements to allocate certain risks to developers.

4. What would a balanced liability system look like to facilitate the uptake of AI?

- Identify categories of products or uses that have defined liability boundaries.
- Develop standards of liability that correspond to technological issues posed by different types of AI (e.g., minimise evidentiary problems associated with proving causation for black-box AI).
- Develop standards of care that encourage physicians to adopt AI technology when it is properly validated but not do so when the risk-benefit calculation is tenuous.

5. What legal issues relating to AI development and design generally impact horizontal regulation of AI across all industries?

- Data privacy is a central concern for manufacturers, physicians, and patients.
- Allocation of responsibility between relevant parties (e.g., manufacturer, physician, and health system) for harms caused by AI-enabled technologies.
- Consistent regulatory treatment of AI technologies.
- Development of practice guidelines that relevant parties (e.g., physicians) can rely on when implementing new AI-enabled technology.

For the remaining term of the project, we anticipate continuing and expanding our goals in WP8. To achieve this aim, we plan to continue publishing cutting-edge articles in leading journals (Task 8.4), focusing on liability and other ethical and legal issues arising from the development, adoption, and use of AI-assisted or autonomous medical tools. This will inform policymakers and other stakeholders about the significant medical, ethical, and legal concerns surrounding those tools.

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